

SURVEY ASSESSMENT DATA GOVERNANCE FOR PUBLIC SECTOR IN COLOMBIA

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this survey is to analyze the current situation of data governance in the different organizations of the Colombian State, in such a way that it allows to know the baseline, in order to carry out an adequate implementation or update in their data governance projects. It is aimed at public sector employees with positions related to the area of information technology, information systems, data management or computer science.

The general concept of data governance was used as an introduction to the survey, where it refers to a set of processes, policies, rules and controls that are established in an organization to ensure the proper management of data. The main objective is to ensure that data is used effectively, reliably and securely to support data-driven decision making, leverage its strategic value, and improve operational efficiency, supporting the achievement of the organization's objectives and the fulfillment of its mission.

After reading and understanding the Informed Consent, do you agree to participate in the study?

- Yes
- No

1. SECTION CHARACTERIZATION

Which of the following positions is your job level? *

- Analyst
- Coordinator or Supervisor
- Manager or Director
- Professional
- Other:

Specific Position:

Years of experience in the position:

Education (undergraduate degree, graduate degree):

Name of the State Entity where you work: (Not Required): Type of Entity:

- Territorial
- National

Municipality:

Sector of the organization

- Treasury
- Justice
- Public Administration
- Education and Culture
- Health
- Transportation
- IT/ Technology Services
- Industrial/ Commercial
- Other

How many employees work at the Entity (include all types of relationship)

- 0-50

- o 51-249
- o 250-500
- o 501-1000
- o More than 1000

2. SECTION STRUCTURE ORGANIZATION AND OBJECTIVES DATA GOVERNANCE

Does the entity have an IT area in its organizational structure?

- o Yes
- o No
- o Do not know

If yes, is there an area dedicated to information management or data management throughout its life cycle?

- o Yes
- o No
- o Do not know
- o Not applicable

Does the Entity's top management recognize the importance of Data Governance and fully support the IT area in the achievement of the institutional DG project?

- o Recognizes the importance, but does not support the IT area
- o Supports, but does not recognize the importance of DG
- o Supports and recognizes the importance
- o None of the above
- o Do not know

The Entity has a leader responsible for the strategy and use of data and also has a strategy for the use and exploitation of data.

- o No, the Entity does not have a Leader
- o No, but we are initiating the strategy in the use and exploitation of data.
- o We have a leader, but we have not yet defined the strategy.
- o We have a Leader, but he is not fully dedicated to the role and strategy.
- o We have a fully dedicated Data Leader and a clear data strategy is defined.
- o Do not know

Does the Entity have a budget allocated for data management?

- o Less than 50 million
- o Between 51 and 200 million
- o More than 201 million
- o No budget
- o Do not know

Does the Entity understand the importance of the value of data for its management?

- o The value of the data is not clear
- o It is understood, but there is no use of the data.
- o The data are understood and partially exploited.
- o It is understood, and the data are fully exploited.

What is the scope of the data managed in the State entity?

- o The Entity makes use of internal data (generated by its IS/IT).
- o The Entity makes use of external data (generated by other Entities).
- o The Entity makes use of both internal and external data.
- o No defined data scope
- o Do not know

Data literacy refers to the ability to read, understand, analyze and use data effectively. It involves having the skills to collect, interpret and communicate numerical and statistical information, as well as the ability to use technological tools and analytical methodologies to make effective use of data. Is data literacy a priority for the Entity?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agreed
- Strongly agree

Is the Entity's decision-making based on the data generated as a result of the provision of citizen services and its mission?

- No, we do not prioritize data in decision making
- No, but we are moving in that direction
- No, but we use data in some strategic decisions.
- Yes, data plays an important role in decision making.
- Yes, our organization uses data operationally, tactically and strategically.
- Do not know

11. What strategies or regulations does the Entity use for the management of institutional data?

- Guide to Open Data in Colombia FURAG
- Conpes 3920 of Big Data
- Conpes 3975 - National Digital Transformation and Artificial Intelligence Policy
- Conpes 3854 Colombia's National Digital Security Policy
- G.INF.06-Technical Guide to Information - Data Governance
- PNID- National Plan for Data Infrastructure
- Resolution 3564 of 2015 - related aspects Transparency and Access to Public Information Law.
- Decree 1008 of 2018 - general guidelines of the Digital Government policy (MINTIC).
- Decree 2106 of 2019 - Digital Transformation For Effective Public Management
- Do not know
- Others:

3. SECTION STAKEHOLDERS FOR DATA GOVERNANCE

Has the Entity conducted analysis and research to identify the Stakeholders for the most relevant data in the organization?

- Stakeholders have not been identified
- Stakeholders have been partially identified
- Stakeholders have been fully identified and feedback on the process is available.
- Do not know

Does the Entity know the needs and expectations of the Stakeholders?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agreed
- Strongly agree

14. Does the entity have mechanisms for face-to-face communication or virtual interaction (interviews) to manage and socialize the management of institutional information with its stakeholders?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agreed
- Strongly agree

How much does the government entity ensure that its relevant stakeholders are heard and taken into account in the planning and execution of its data management projects and programs?

- Very Frequently
- Frequently
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Never

What measures has the Entity taken to involve its relevant stakeholders in decision making based on institutional data? Stakeholders are not involved in the decision making process.

- Periodic Meetings
- Consultations and Interviews
- Working Groups and Participation in Committees
- Do not know

What is the level of knowledge you have about information management and data governance in relation to the different stakeholders?

- No knowledge
- Basic
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Do not know

4. SECTION PROCESSES AND PROCEDURES IN DATA GOVERNANCE.

Does the Entity have an inventory, identified and documented of the business processes that allow to know the traceability of the institutional data cycle?

- No inventory
- There is an undocumented partial inventory
- There is a documented partial inventory
- A complete and documented inventory is available
- Do not know

Does the entity have a committee, or whoever takes its place, to manage compliance with the norms and regulations established by the state regarding the implementation of data governance projects?

- There is no committee
- A committee is in place, but data management projects are not monitored.
- Data governance projects are managed, but not carried out by committee.
- Do not know

Has the Entity defined a specific institutional data management project that includes a scope, objectives, goals and schedule as suggested in document G.INF?06 Information Technical Guide - Data Governance, from MINTIC?

- Data management activities are being carried out, but there is NO defined project.
- Data management projects are available partially or independently for specific needs.
- The MINTIC data governance technical guide is unknown
- Do not know

Has the Entity defined a data governance framework that includes objective, principles, roles, responsibilities, actors, and data custodians, in the Institution?

- No data governance framework in place
- Not currently in place, but a DG implementation is planned.
- A partial governance framework is in place
- A full governance framework is in place
- Do not know

Standardized and normalized data is the transformation and adjustment of the data used to make them more comparable, interpretable and suitable for analysis and processing. Are the data produced by the service of the institutional functions *standardized and normalized?

- They are not standardized or normalized.
- They are standardized and partially standardized
- They are standardized and normalized
- Do not know

About processes , standards and mechanism:

	Very Frequently	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never
Does the Entity have defined processes or procedures for data capture, storage, updating, access and final disposition?					
Has the Entity defined the standards and guidelines for data quality in the Institution?					
Has the Entity defined the mechanisms for control and audit of institutional data?					
Has the Entity considered measures to establish the security and privacy of information to ensure the protection of Institutional data?					
Does the entity contemplate mechanisms to socialize, train and raise awareness among personnel regarding data governance policies and standards?					

5. SECTION EVALUATION OF SYSTEMS, TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR RISKS

Does the Entity have what types of centralized information systems and/or technological tools to manage data in the State entity?

- No centralized system
- Business management systems (ERP/CRM)
- Human Resources Management Systems (HRIS)
- Supply chain management system (SCM)
- Business Intelligence System (BI)

- o Other support systems
- o Do not know

Analytical methods and techniques refer to methods that can create prediction, prescription, regression, or machine learning based on data. Is the Entity aware of which analytical methods and techniques to add value to institutional data?

- o No knowledge of any analytical methods or techniques
- o Descriptive Analytics (descriptive dashboards)
- o Diagnostic Analytics (data mining, business intelligence),
- o Predictive Analytics (artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, forecasting, optimization)
- o Do not know

Does the Entity plan to implement technologies that facilitate the interpretation of knowledge in analytical methods and techniques to add value to institutional data?

- o There are no plans to implement any technology
- o There are plans to implement data management technologies, but there is no budget.
- o Data management technologies are planned to be implemented, and the designated budget is available.
- o Do not know
- o Another

About systems and risk

	Very Frequently	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never
Does the entity actively have an information security risk management plan?					
Has the entity implemented data analysis tools for decision making?					
Does the Entity analyze how risks associated with the use and management of data are managed?					
Has the entity estimated the costs necessary to implement or support enterprise data management?					

How does the Entity ensure that the auditing and control processes of the chosen technological solutions are effective?

- o There are no IS/IT audit and control processes.
- o Technical requirements of the solution are made, based on the business rules.
- o Audit and control processes are in place, but their effectiveness is not measured.
- o Do not know
- o Not applicable

When implementing technological solutions, how does the Entity ensure that data management is used efficiently in the provision of services to citizens? • No follow-up is performed

- o Data governance is in place
- o Effectiveness indicators are used in the stabilization phases of the IS/IT.

- o Do not know

What measures does the Entity take to ensure the training and technological development of its public employees?

- o There are no training indicators
- o Ongoing IS/IT training and updating processes have been defined.
- o Virtual training platforms are available
- o Do not know
- o Not applicable